

ReenactFaces: A Specialized Dataset for Reenactment-based Deepfake Detection

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Abstract The growing sophistication of deepfake technologies poses a serious threat to the authenticity of digital media and has far-reaching implications for security, privacy and misinformation. Existing deepfake datasets are often limited in scope, with most focusing on a single manipulation technique, and only a few addressing the specific domain of facial-reenactment. To address this gap, we present ReenactFaces, a specialized, open-access dataset designed to support the development and evaluation of deepfake detection systems targeting facial-reenactment methods. This dataset includes both real and manipulated videos, enabling researchers to train and test models specifically against reenactment-based deepfakes. ReenactFaces provides a valuable resource for improving the generalization of detection models to reenactment manipulations, filling a critical gap in the literature and complementing existing deepfake datasets. The dataset is available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/14035828>.

1 Introduction

The rise of deepfake technology, driven by advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning (DL), has transformed the landscape of digital media manipulation [3]. Deepfakes have the capability to alter facial expressions and movements,

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allowing for highly realistic video forgeries. Among various deepfake manipulation techniques, facial-reenactment - the process of mimicking a person’s facial movements in real time - presents unique challenges for detection models. These deepfakes are often used in generating fake speeches, impersonations and other types of media that can be weaponized to create disinformation and harm individual reputations.

As facial-reenactment deepfakes become more sophisticated, the need for specialized detection systems has grown. While existing methods have shown success in detecting other forms of deepfakes such as face-swapping, facial-reenactment detection remains less explored [4]. Many detection models tend to overfit to specific datasets or manipulation techniques, reducing their generalization capability when exposed to new or unseen data. Moreover, the lack of dedicated datasets focusing on reenactment manipulations further hampers progress in this area.

Most publicly available deepfake datasets focus on a single manipulation technique, with only a few providing substantial examples of facial-reenactment [12]. This scarcity limits the ability of detection models to effectively train and generalize on this specific manipulation type, reducing their robustness in real-world applications. To bridge this gap, we introduce ReenactFaces, a dataset entirely dedicated to facial-reenactment deepfakes.

Unlike other datasets where reenactment examples are sparse, ReenactFaces provides an extensive collection of manipulated videos paired with corresponding real footage, designed specifically to capture the unique traits of facial-reenactment. It includes a wide variety of identities, lighting conditions and backgrounds, offering a valuable resource for developing detection models that can generalize effectively across diverse real-world scenarios. By focusing on this often-overlooked manipulation, ReenactFaces fills a crucial gap in deepfake detection, helping to ensure the authenticity of digital media.

The contributions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- ReenactFaces, a novel deepfake dataset focused exclusively on facial-reenactment manipulations, is introduced to support the development of specialized detection models.
- We demonstrate the benefit of incorporating ReenactFaces alongside other widely used deepfake datasets during training, showing consistent improvements in model performance and cross-dataset generalization.
- We offer insights and recommendations for the creation of future deepfake datasets and identify key challenges in detecting facial-reenactment deepfakes, guiding ongoing research efforts.

2 Existing Deepfake Datasets

A variety of datasets have been developed to support the advancement of deepfake video detection techniques. While each dataset has played an important role in driving progress, issues related to scale, diversity, and manipulation types continue to

Table 1 Quantitative comparison of ReenactFaces with existing deepfake datasets. FS: Face-Swapping; FR: Facial-Reenactment

Dataset	Real Videos	Fake Videos	Total Videos	Total Subjects	Manipulation Tools	Real Source
UADFV	49	49	98	49	FS	1 YouTube
Deepfake-TIMIT	640	320	960	32	FS	2 VidTIMIT
FF++	1,000	4,000	5,000	1,000	FS, FR	4 YouTube
Celeb-DF	590	5,639	6,229	59	FS	1 YouTube
DFDC	23,654	104,500	128,154	960	FS	8 Self-Recording
DeeperForensics-1.0	10,000	50,000	60,000	100	FS	1 Self-Recording
ReenactFaces (Ours)	10,000	10,000	20,000	100	FR	3 YouTube

impede the generalization of detection models. UADFV [14], one of the earliest datasets, introduced a modest collection of 49 real and 49 fake videos produced through a simple face-swapping method. Though it served as a useful starting point for early work, its small size and narrow focus on a single manipulation technique make it less suited for today’s more sophisticated detection tasks.

Similarly, the Deepfake-TIMIT dataset [6] provided 640 manipulated videos using two face-swapping methods, but these videos were artificially generated under controlled conditions, lacking the variability seen in real-world scenarios such as lighting, backgrounds and camera angles. FaceForensics++ (FF++) [10] has had a major influence in the field by significantly increasing the available data, comprising 1,000 real and 5,000 manipulated videos across multiple techniques, including both face-swapping and facial-reenactment. While this dataset introduced compression artifacts to emulate real-world video conditions, it remains limited in the variety of manipulation techniques and identities it covers.

The Celeb-DF dataset [7] made a significant contribution with 5,639 high-quality deepfake videos generated from celebrity footage, focusing on face-swaps. However, the limited number of unique identities in the dataset may restrict the ability of models trained on it to generalize well. Moreover, the DeepFake Detection Challenge (DFDC) dataset [2], launched by Facebook, represented a substantial step forward, with over 100,000 videos created using various manipulation methods. Despite its size, the dataset is dominated by face-swaps and lacks a structured comparison between real and fake versions of individual videos, which is crucial for binary classification tasks.

Lastly, DeeperForensics-1.0 [5] aimed to overcome some of these challenges by offering a large-scale dataset with 50,000 manipulated and 10,000 authentic videos, produced using high-quality face-swapping techniques. The dataset includes a range of real-world conditions, such as different lighting setups, camera angles and compression artifacts, making it more reflective of real-world deepfake detection challenges. However, despite its variety, DeeperForensics still focuses exclusively on face-swapping, which limits its application for evaluating detection models targeting other forms of manipulation, such as facial-reenactment or lip-syncing. Table 1 offers a quantitative comparison of ReenactFaces with these established deepfake datasets.

3 Methodology

3.1 Real Video Collection

To build a robust dataset of real facial videos for our study, we curated a collection of videos from YouTube, featuring a wide range of individuals of diverse ethnic backgrounds and age groups. This selection ensures that our dataset encompasses various facial features, expressions and movements, offering a rich foundation for facial-reenactment. The steps involved in the collection and processing of these videos are detailed below.

The initial step involved retrieving high-quality interview-style videos, which typically feature extended, uninterrupted appearances of an individual "X". To gather these, we conducted keyword-based searches in the format "X interview" or similar. After downloading the videos, we extracted individual frames and applied a face detection algorithm using a fine-tuned version of the YOLOv8n [8] model. This model was specifically trained to detect human faces with high precision.

For each frame, the face detection algorithm was employed and only frames with a single detected face were retained. Frames featuring multiple individuals were discarded to maintain focus on the target person. Consecutive frames where a single face was consistently detected were grouped into continuous segments. This allowed us to create video segments that highlight the facial appearance of a single individual throughout.

For uniformity, these continuous segments were then further divided based on duration. Specifically, any segment exceeding a duration of five times the frame rate was split into subsegments of equal length. Shorter segments that did not meet this criterion were discarded, as they were deemed too brief for effective use in facial-reenactment tasks.

Finally, the resulting video segments were manually reviewed to ensure quality and relevance. This step involved discarding any segments that did not feature the intended individual, as well as those where the person's face remained static (e.g., still images or photographs). This process yielded a high-quality dataset showcasing diverse facial movements, expressions and poses.

3.2 Deepfake Video Creation

Using the collected dataset of real videos, we generated facial-reenactment videos through a structured pipeline. This section details the key steps involved in the process.

For each video segment, the first step was to accurately track the target individual's face across all frames. We utilized the YOLOv8n-face model for this purpose, storing the bounding box coordinates for the upper-left and bottom-right corners

of the detected face in each frame. This face-tracking procedure ensured consistent detection of the facial region throughout the video sequence.

Next, we calculated the minimum and maximum boundaries for the bounding boxes across all frames in a segment, ensuring the face remained within these bounds. To account for slight movements and ensure complete coverage of the face, we expanded the bounding box by a scaling factor of 1.3. This scaling introduced a margin around the face, which is essential for accurate facial-reenactment.

Using the scaled bounding box, we then cropped the face region from each frame. If the bounding box exceeded the frame boundaries, the affected frames were excluded from further processing to avoid artifacts or distortions in the final reenacted videos. This step ensured the integrity of the cropped facial regions.

With the face region isolated, we established source-target pairs for facial-reenactment. The source video provides the facial movements and expressions to be transferred to the target video. For enhanced realism, we used a pose-matching technique to ensure that the source image closely resembles the target frame. Specifically, we extracted five key facial landmarks - eyes, nose and mouth corners - from both the source and the target videos. By minimizing the Euclidean distance between these landmarks, we selected the source frame with the closest facial pose to the target frame. This approach led to more natural and visually coherent facial-reenactment results.

3.3 Facial-Reenactment Tools

We employed three state-of-the-art facial-reenactment tools to generate the final reenacted videos. Each tool was carefully selected to capture diverse aspects of facial movements and expressions, contributing to the realism and quality of the generated content.

The first tool we used is the First-Order Motion Model [13]. This model uses learned keypoints and local affine transformations to capture the motion dynamics of the source face and transfer them to the target. An occlusion-aware generator is integrated into the model to handle situations where parts of the face are not visible, ensuring smooth and realistic reenactment even in the presence of occlusions.

The second tool is the Thin-Plate Spline Motion Model [15]. This model uses keypoint detectors to predict the positions of key facial landmarks from both the source and driving video. The detected keypoints are then used to create thin-plate spline transformations, which effectively transfer complex facial movements. Additionally, the model includes a background motion predictor, and a dense motion network to handle background consistency and occlusions.

The third tool, FSRT [9], leverages keypoints and expressions extracted from source images to create latent representations, which are processed by a Transformer-based architecture. This model effectively transfers expressions from the source to the target by conditioning the Transformer decoder on the driving keypoints and fa-

Fig. 1 Overview of the facial-reenactment process.

cial expressions. The use of Transformers allows for precise control and generation of highly realistic facial-reenactments.

Fig. 1 illustrates the facial-reenactment process, where the facial expressions from a source identity are transferred to a target identity using the aforementioned tools.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Experimental Setup

We evaluated the performance of three commonly used deepfake detection models — MesoNet [1], ResNet and EfficientNet — on two highly cited datasets for deepfake detection: FF++ and Celeb-DF. FF++ contains a mix of face-swapping and facial-reenactment manipulations, while Celeb-DF focuses exclusively on face-swapping. Each model was trained and tested separately on both the FF++ and Celeb-DF datasets.

In addition to these direct comparisons, we also conducted an experiment to assess whether our proposed dataset, ReenactFaces, could aid model generalization when combined with Celeb-DF. This combination aimed to create a training dataset with a broader range of manipulation types, allowing models to potentially learn a richer set of features and generalize better on datasets containing mixed manipulation types, such as FF++. This design choice addresses the scarcity of reenactment-focused datasets, which limits detection capabilities.

EfficientNet, notable for being part of the winning solution DFDC by Seferbekov et al. [11], and ResNet were initialized with ImageNet-pretrained weights, while

MesoNet was trained from scratch. All models underwent 10 epochs of training with an initial learning rate of 0.001, optimized with the Adam algorithm and cosine annealing to adjust the learning rate progressively. Due to memory constraints, batch sizes were set to 512 for MesoNet and ResNet and 32 for EfficientNet. We applied binary cross-entropy loss to align with the task’s binary classification nature.

4.2 Results

The performance of the deepfake detection models is summarized in Tables 2 and 3, which report the AUC and accuracy metrics based on the aforementioned experimental design.

Table 2 AUC (%) comparison of the deepfake detection models.

Training Dataset	MesoNet		ResNet		EfficientNet	
	FF++	Celeb-DF	FF++	Celeb-DF	FF++	Celeb-DF
FF++	92	69	97	70	99	75
Celeb-DF	64	99	63	99	64	100
Celeb-DF + ReenactFaces	62	94	65	100	66	100

Table 3 Accuracy (%) comparison of the deepfake detection models.

Training Dataset	MesoNet		ResNet		EfficientNet	
	FF++	Celeb-DF	FF++	Celeb-DF	FF++	Celeb-DF
FF++	88	69	94	73	99	75
Celeb-DF	35	95	32	98	28	99
Celeb-DF + ReenactFaces	53	89	37	99	51	97

The results suggest that when models are trained on a single dataset, they adapt effectively to the specific characteristics and manipulation types within that dataset. This is evident from EfficientNet’s high AUC values of 99% on FF++ and 100% on Celeb-DF, as well as its accuracy of 99% on both datasets. ResNet also demonstrates strong performance within individual datasets, achieving AUC scores of 97% on FF++ and 99% on Celeb-DF. MesoNet, while generally lower in performance compared to EfficientNet and ResNet, still achieved an AUC of 92% on FF++, showing it can capture key features for detecting deepfakes within FF++ data.

However, when models trained on one dataset are tested on the other, performance decreases substantially. For instance, EfficientNet’s AUC dropped from 99% on FF++ to 75% when tested on Celeb-DF, and ResNet’s AUC decreased from 97% to 70%. This trend is even more evident when models are trained on Celeb-DF and tested on FF++. For example, EfficientNet’s AUC dropped from 100% on Celeb-DF

to 64% on FF++, while ResNet’s AUC fell from 99% to 63%. These results indicate that the unique characteristics of each dataset lead to difficulties in generalization across different data distributions.

When training incorporates the ReenactFaces dataset alongside Celeb-DF, the results show a consistent improvement, suggesting that the additional facial-reenactment data enhances model performance across both datasets, as evidenced by ResNet achieving an AUC of 100% and EfficientNet maintaining a strong AUC of 100%. This indicates that incorporating ReenactFaces does not interfere with the model’s ability to detect face-swapping manipulations. In fact, the additional data appears to bolster the model’s capacity to generalize to reenactment patterns, with both ResNet and EfficientNet exhibiting no decrease in performance on Celeb-DF. The slight decrease noted for MesoNet could be attributed to its relatively smaller model size and limited capacity to learn the more complex patterns introduced by the additional reenactment data.

The inclusion of ReenactFaces also leads to noticeable improvements in model performance on the FF++ dataset. Specifically, models trained with the combined Celeb-DF + ReenactFaces dataset show a significant increase in accuracy: for MesoNet, accuracy improved from 35% to 53%, and for EfficientNet, accuracy rose from 28% to 51%. The AUC for ResNet also rose from 63% to 65%, and EfficientNet saw an increase from 64% to 66%, further supporting the positive impact of adding ReenactFaces on cross-dataset generalization. These improvements suggest that the ReenactFaces dataset introduces valuable diversity, particularly in reenactment-based manipulations, allowing models to better capture features associated with both face-swapping and facial-reenactment manipulations.

Overall, the improved generalization between FF++ and Celeb-DF when incorporating ReenactFaces highlights the benefits of training with a more diverse set of manipulations. This demonstrates the potential of ReenactFaces as a complementary dataset for multi-type deepfake training, allowing models to learn a broader range of transformation patterns. As a result, models trained with ReenactFaces exhibit greater robustness in detecting various types of deepfakes, particularly in scenarios where both face-swapping and facial-reenactment manipulations are present.

5 Discussion

The creation of large, diverse datasets is crucial to advancing the field of deepfake detection. By developing a resource as proposed in this study, researchers could more effectively benchmark and improve their algorithms, especially as generative models continue to evolve. A dataset that reflects real-world challenges, such as demographic diversity and varying facial poses, can enhance model robustness, enabling better generalization across different populations and use cases.

As the landscape of deepfake technology advances, new algorithms and techniques for generating realistic deepfakes continue to emerge, often leveraging the latest advancements in AI. By including a diverse range of generation techniques,

such as Transformers, GANs and autoencoders, the dataset can encompass a broader spectrum of potential manipulations, allowing researchers to evaluate detection algorithms against a wide array of scenarios and maintain effectiveness as new methods arise.

Apart from dataset creation, another major challenge lies in developing detection methods capable of adapting to increasingly sophisticated forgeries. Ensuring that these methods generalize well across datasets remains a key issue, as models often perform well on specific datasets but struggle with unseen or real-world data. Utilizing multiple datasets during training (as demonstrated in this study with ReenactFaces and Celeb-DF), along with transfer learning and domain adaptation techniques, could help address this problem, improving models' ability to detect deepfakes in diverse, real-world scenarios.

Furthermore, cross-modal methods that analyze audio, video and textual data simultaneously may also prove more effective in detecting inconsistencies and subtle signs of manipulation, enhancing the overall robustness of detection systems. By examining audio-visual correlations, for example, models can identify mismatches between lip movements and speech, which are often difficult to detect through visual analysis alone.

Model interpretability is also crucial, particularly for high-stakes applications like law enforcement and media verification. Transparent detection models that explain their decision-making process are vital for building trust among users and ensuring the responsible application of these systems. Ethical considerations surrounding data use and privacy must also be addressed, especially when using real individuals in datasets.

Finally, as deepfake technology becomes more widespread, public awareness and education will be crucial in mitigating the risks. Public outreach on deepfake technologies can help individuals critically evaluate media and avoid manipulation. Moreover, collaboration between researchers, media organizations and law enforcement is essential for developing tools, policies and legal frameworks to prevent the malicious use of deepfakes.

6 Conclusions

As deepfake technology becomes more advanced, the need for more sophisticated datasets becomes increasingly important. This study proposes a specialized dataset aimed at reenactment-based deepfakes, addressing gaps in existing resources and offering researchers a robust tool for developing detection models. By providing diverse, high-quality content, this dataset can be used in conjunction with existing ones, serving as a supplementary resource to improve model accuracy and generalization. In addition to its practical value, this work offers valuable insights into the design of comprehensive deepfake datasets, while highlighting critical challenges in the field and guiding further advancements.

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